

Dehydrogenation and Hydrogenation of Hydrocarbons over Platinum-Alumina Catalysts

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Cyclohexane and cyclohexene are dehydrogenated over platinum-alumina catalysts containing varying amounts of platinum and platinum-alumina doped with fluoride and caesium ions in the temperature range 250 to 350°, while benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and *p*-cymene are hydrogenated over platinum-alumina D in the temperature range 80 to 250°. The rate of dehydrogenation increases with increasing contact time, registers a maximum around 0.9 hr and then begins to fall. Increase of temperature increases the conversion of cyclohexane over catalysts D and I while it decreases the conversion over catalyst G.

Initial addition of platinum upto 0.9% has a beneficial effect on the reactions of cyclohexane and cyclohexene. Subsequent additions bring down the conversions of both. Even though the activity of the catalyst varies with platinum content, its ability to catalyse the conversion of cyclohexene is always more than that of cyclohexane irrespective of platinum concentration.

Addition of caesium increases the performance of platinum-alumina whereas addition of hydrogen fluoride decreases it. Cyclohexane formation from cyclohexene by disproportionation increases in the presence of hydrofluoric acid and decreases in the presence of caesium.

Hydrogenation increases in each case with temperature, exhibits a maximum and then falls down. The rate of hydrogenation decreases with substitution of alkyl groups.

PLATINUM-ALUMINA being a reforming catalyst has been used extensively to catalyse a large variety of reactions¹, such, as hydrogenation, dehydrogenation, dehydrocyclization, dehydroisomerization etc. The physical properties of these catalysts such as surface area, porosity, dispersion and distribution of platinum metal on the support have been studied in relation to the methods of their preparation² which in turn correlated to their ability to catalyse the above reactions³⁻⁵. In this work, a comparative study of the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane, the dehydrogenation and disproportionation of cyclohexene as well as hydrogenation of benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, and *p*-cymene have been investigated over platinum-alumina containing varying amounts of platinum and platinum-alumina modified with caesium and fluoride ions in order to evaluate the optimum conditions for the above closely related reactions.

Experimental

Preparation of Catalysts :

Alumina (Catalyst A) : Alumina was prepared by hydrolysing aluminium isopropoxide (BDH, AR) with distilled water⁶. The precipitated aluminium hydroxide was filtered, washed thoroughly and dried at 120° for 24 hrs, cooled and sieved to 150-170 mesh, calcined at 400° for 8 hrs and then used as support for platinum.

Platinum-Alumina : Platinum-alumina catalysts, B, C, D, E and F were obtained by adding calculated volumes of chloroplatinic acid in water to five weighed samples of alumina A to give respectively 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9 and 1.4% platinum by weight (confirmed by spectrophotometric analysis⁷). The slurry was stirred for 3 hrs and dried at 120° for 24 hrs. The temperature was raised slowly, while passing pure dry hydrogen to reach 500° in a period of 2 hrs and kept at this temperature for 8 hrs. The activated material was powdered and pelletised to 4 × 4 mm size pellets.

Platinum-Alumina-HF (Catalysts G and H) : Catalysts G and H were prepared by impregnating platinum-alumina catalyst D with appropriate volumes of hydrofluoric acid (40% E. Merck) to give 5 and 10% by weights of hydrogen fluoride in the catalyst respectively. The particle size of the catalyst used was of the range 16-30 mesh.

Platinum-Alumina-Caesium Oxide (Catalysts I, J and K) : Catalysts I, J and K were obtained by doping catalyst D with requisite volume of caesium nitrate solution in water to give respectively 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5% caesium by weight in the catalyst. The particle size in this case also was 16-30 mesh. The procedures described earlier was followed for drying and activation.

Platinized Asbestos : A solution of 1.25 g of chloroplatinic acid in 50 ml of water was prepared. To this solution 45 g of asbestos was added. Hydrogen was bubbled vigorously through the solution for reduction. Hydrogen bubbling was continued for 15 minutes after the disappearance of the yellow colour of the chloroplatinic acid, to ensure complete reduction.

Preparation of Materials : Cyclohexane, benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene and *p*-cymene were BDH samples. They were distilled before use and their purity was checked by gas chromatograph. Cyclohexene was prepared by dehydrating cyclohexanol according to the method described in Vogel⁸. Purified hydrogen (Indian Oxygen Co.) was used.

Apparatus and Procedure : The reactions were carried out at atmospheric pressure in an integral fixed bed Pyrex flow type reactor, 50 cm long and 1.5 cm internal diameter. The pre-heater was made in the form of a spiral wound uniformly around the reactor covering half of its length, to ensure complete vaporisation of the liquid before entering into the reactor tube. Above the catalyst bed Pyrex glass beads (4 mm diameter) were placed to a height of 5 cm. The reactor tube was inserted into a cylindrical furnace and heated electrically to the requisite temperature.

Prior to each run the catalyst was reactivated by heating for 8 hrs in a current of dry air at 500°; it was then reduced by passing pure dry hydrogen for 6 hrs at the same temperature and then brought to the requisite experimental temperature. Initial experiments conducted both over oxidised and reduced catalysts did not show any significant variations in the product distributions. Therefore subsequent runs were conducted over oxidised catalysts. For hydrogenation, purified hydrogen was passed at the rate of 200 ml per minute in all cases.

The reactant liquid was fed into the reactor by a constant feed infusion pump that could displace 10 ml of the liquid per hour. The various contact times were achieved by varying the weight of the catalyst.

The liquid products collected for the first 15 minutes of each run which normally covers an hour, was discarded and analysis was made only of the products collected after this time.

The liquid products were identified using chemical and gas chromatographic methods. The products were quantitatively estimated by an AIMIL gas chromatographic column consisting of a one meter column of carbowax on chromosorb. The column temperature for the best resolution within a reasonable time was found to be 80° with nitrogen inlet pressure of 20 psi using hydrogen as fuel for the flame ionization detector. For the identification

of different peaks in the chromatogram retention times for the different compounds were found by introducing authentic samples. For quantitative analysis synthetic mixtures containing the compounds in varying proportions were introduced and calibration curves relating the concentration with peak heights were drawn. Since the peaks obtained were sharp and symmetrical, peak heights were used as a measure of concentration.

Surface area : The surface area measurements of catalysts D, E and F were made according to BET method by adsorption of nitrogen at liquid nitrogen temperature. The experimental procedure and calculations were the same as described by Emmett⁹. The values for catalysts D, E and F were found to be 121.1, 171.7 and 230.7 m²/g respectively. The platinum metal area for the above three catalysts were found to be 30.5, 48.4 and 58.5 m²/g of catalyst respectively by carbon monoxide adsorption according to the procedure of Dorling¹⁰.

Estimation of Carbon : The carbon deposited on the surface of the catalyst during the dehydrogenation reaction has been determined from the amount of CO₂ obtained on regeneration of the catalyst by passing the oxides of carbon through a heated platinized asbestos column kept at about 500°. The CO₂ formed was estimated by absorption in excess of alkali of known concentration and back titration and the results are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1

Catalyst	Composition
A	Alumina (from aluminium isopropoxide)
B	Alumina+0.1% Platinum
C	Alumina+0.3% Platinum
D	Alumina+0.6% Platinum
E	Alumina+0.9% Platinum
F	Alumina+1.4% Platinum
G	Alumina+0.6% Pt+5.0% HF
H	Alumina+0.6% Pt+10% HF
I	Alumina+0.6% Pt+0.5% Cs
J	Alumina+0.6% Pt+1.0% Cs
K	Alumina+0.6% Pt+1.5% Cs

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF CARBON AFTER DEHYDROGENATION OF CYCLOHEXANE

Pretreatment I : Catalyst regenerated at 500° in air for 8 hrs.
Pretreatment II : Catalyst regenerated at 500° in air for 8 hrs followed by reduction for 6 hrs in dry hydrogen.

Catalyst	Temperature °C	Pretreatment I	Pretreatment II
0.6% Pt	250	0.06%	0.05%
	300	0.6 %	0.5 %
	350	0.7 %	0.6 %
0.89%	250	0.08%	0.08%
	300	0.5 %	0.4 %
	350	0.6 %	0.5 %
1.4%	250	0.08%	0.06%
	300	0.6 %	0.6 %
	350	0.7 %	0.6 %

Results and Discussion

Dehydrogenation of cyclohexane and cyclohexene :

Contact time : The influence of contact time, W/F (where W is the weight of the catalyst and F is the flow rate of cyclohexane passed per hour) has been studied over catalyst D (0.6% Pt) at 250, 300 and 350° and the results are presented in Fig. 1. The conversion of cyclohexane is found to increase with increasing contact time, registering a maximum around 0.9 hr and then begins to fall reaching a minimum. For instance at 300° the amount of cyclohexane reacted at 0.16 hr is 27%. It increases to 73% around 0.9 hr which comes down to 44% at 2.4 hr. The decrease in the conversion of cyclohexane in the higher contact time regions is quite understandable.

Fig. 1. Dehydrogenation of cyclohexane over Platinum-alumina catalyst D; Effect of contact time at 250, 300 and 350°.

x—250°, Δ—300°, ⊙—350°.

During this investigation involving dehydrogenation and hydrogenation of hydrocarbons, no olefinic intermediates such as cyclohexene, cyclohexadiene were detected although the gas chromatograph used can detect these intermediates under the conditions of analysis. To check the absence of olefinic intermediates in the products, the dehydrogenation of menthanes (substituted derivatives of cyclohexane) to cymenes over this catalyst under similar conditions has been carried out¹¹. Here too no menthenes and menthadienes have been detected. The activation energy for the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane is calculated to be

10.6 kcal/mole assuming that it is zero order reaction.

Influence of Temperature : Fig. 2 presents the influence of temperature on the conversion of cyclohexane over alumina impregnated with 0.6% platinum (catalyst D) and two other catalysts G and I obtained by modifying D with 5% HF and 0.5 caesium respectively at a constant contact time of 0.79 hr. With increasing temperature from 250 to 300° the rate of conversion increases almost linearly over all the three catalysts. Further increase of temperature from 300 to 350°, produces significant variations in the activity pattern. For instance over catalyst I an almost regular increase is maintained while over catalyst D only a small negligible enhancement is noted whereas the dehydrogenation activity of catalyst G decreases in this temperature regions.

Fig. 2. Dehydrogenation of cyclohexane over catalysts D, G and I; Effect of Temperature. Contact time 0.79 hr.

⊙—Catalyst—D, Δ—Catalyst—G, x—Catalyst—I.

Platinum Concentration : The effect of platinum concentration on the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane has been studied at 250, 300 and 350° at a contact time of 0.79 hr and the results are presented in Fig. 3 while the distribution of products from cyclohexene at 250° is given in Fig. 4. The amounts of cyclohexane and cyclohexene reacted under identical conditions are compared in Fig. 5.

The dehydrogenating ability of the catalyst increases with increasing platinum content up to 0.9% platinum at all the three temperatures (Fig. 3) and above this concentration the activity comes down. The performance of the catalyst is found

Fig. 8. Dehydrogenation of cyclohexane over Platinum-alumina catalysts; Effect of Platinum concentration at 250, 300 and 350°. Contact time 0.79 hr. ○—250°, △—300°, ×—350°.

Fig. 4. Dehydrogenation of Cyclohexene over Platinum-alumina Catalysts; Effect of Platinum concentration on the product distribution. Contact time 0.79 hr, Temperature 250°. ●—Cyclohexene Unchanged, ▲—Cyclohexene, ×—Benzene.

to be better above 300° as the dehydrogenation is thermodynamically unfavourable in the lower temperature regions¹³. The shapes of the plots of percentage conversion versus platinum concentration given in Fig. 5 for cyclohexane and cyclohexene are similar though the amount of cyclohexene reacted at each platinum concentration is higher.

Fig. 5. Dehydrogenation of Cyclohexane and Cyclohexene over Platinum-alumina; Effect of Platinum concentration, Contact time 0.79 hr., Temperature 250°. ○—Cyclohexane, △—Cyclohexene.

According to Maatman the activity of platinum-alumina catalyst is proportional to platinum metal area and not platinum concentration¹⁸. The metal surface area for catalysts D, E and F as determined by carbon monoxide adsorption¹⁰ are 5083, 5377 and 3464 m²/g of platinum metal and the corresponding amount of cyclohexane reacted over these catalysts at 300° are 73, 82 and 37% respectively which are quite in order.

Increasing concentration of platinum is also found to bring down the dehydrogenation of cyclohexene (Fig. 4) but at each platinum concentration the amount of cyclohexene reacted is more than that of cyclohexane as can be seen for Fig. 5. From these observations it is obvious that the creation of first unsaturation in a saturated ring compound appears to be difficult. Similar observation was made by Nigam¹⁴.

Up to a concentration of 0.9% platinum the amount of cyclohexane formed as a result of disproportionation of cyclohexene remains constant while

the formation of benzene increases. Above this critical concentration of platinum, the proportion of both cyclohexane and benzene in the product comes down. The increased formation of benzene is quite understandable from the fact that it is formed from cyclohexene by parallel reactions involving disproportionation and dehydrogenation even though the interconversion of benzene and cyclohexane is quite possible. The fall in the activity of the catalyst with higher platinum concentration would appear to be due to the increased crystallite size of platinum metal over the support. From Figs. 3 to 5, it can be noticed that 0.9% platinum appears to be critical beyond which the activity tends to decrease for the system.

Influence of fluoride and caesium ions: With a view to compare the influence of fluoride ions on the conversion of cyclohexane and cyclohexene the amount of each reacted at 350°, are illustrated in Fig. 6. The effect of caesium ions on the reaction of cyclohexene is also included in the same figure while the effects of fluoride and caesium ions on the distribution of products from cyclohexene are given in Tables 3 and 4 respectively.

Fig. 6. Dehydrogenation of Cyclohexane and Cyclohexene over Platinum-alumina Catalysts D, G, H, I, J and K; Effects of Hydrofluoric acid and Caesium. Contact time 0.79 hr., Temperature 350°.

○—Cyclohexane, △—Cyclohexene.

Impregnation of catalyst D with hydrofluoric acid, though reduces the conversion of both cyclohexane and cyclohexene the extent to which they are reduced are not the same. For instance the

TABLE 3—DEHYDROGENATION OF CYCLOHEXENE; EFFECT OF HYDROGEN FLUORIDE. TEMP 350°; CONTACT TIME 0.79 hr

% Hydrogen fluoride	Composition (mole%)		
	Cyclohexene unchanged	Cyclohexane	Benzene
0.0	30	10	60
5.0	40	18	42
10.0	20	20	60

TABLE 4—DEHYDROGENATION OF CYCLOHEXENE; EFFECT OF CAESIUM. TEMP. 350°; CONTACT TIME 0.79 hr

% Caesium	Composition (mole%)		
	Cyclohexene unchanged	Cyclohexane	Benzene
0.0	30	10	60
0.5	19	20	61
1.0	20	16	64
1.5	30	15	55

amount of cyclohexane and cyclohexene reacted over catalyst D are 63 and 70% respectively. Modification of this catalyst with 5% HF reduces the values to 35 and 65% respectively. A further increase of HF concentration to 10% brings down the conversions to 0 and 43% respectively (Fig. 6). On the other hand addition of caesium increases the conversion of cyclohexene (Fig. 6 and Table 4).

An important observation worth mentioning at this junction is the inactivity or stability of cyclohexane when passed over platinum-alumina catalyst modified with HF. It resists reaction. When cyclohexene is passed over this catalyst, it disproportionates in such a way that the concentration of cyclohexane in the product increases (Table 3). Instead of hydrofluoric acid when caesium is added to the catalyst the concentration of cyclohexane in the product is found to decrease (Table 4). This observation confirms the fact that stronger acid sites facilitate the disproportionation reactions involving hydrogen transfer.

In an earlier investigation consisting of the dehydrogenation of 3-carene over chromia-alumina catalyst the formation of menthanes (substituted derivative of cyclohexane) was found to increase when chromia-alumina was modified with hydrofluoric acid¹⁵. This confirms further the observations of the present investigation. It is therefore evident that in the presence of hydrofluoric acid saturated rings are less reactive than unsaturated rings.

Benzene is hydrogenated over platinum-alumina catalyst D (0.6% Pt) in the temperature range 80 to 250°, keeping the contact time at 0.79 hr and the amount reacted are given in Table 5. Toluene, *o*-xylene and *p*-cymene are also hydrogenated under similar conditions and the results are included in the same table with a view to compare the

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE CONVERSIONS OF BENZENE, TOLUENE, *o*-XYLENE AND *p*-CYMENE CONTACT TIME 0.79 hr

Temp °C	Conversion (mole %)			
	Benzene	Toluene	<i>o</i> -Xylene	<i>p</i> -Cymene
80	50	—	—	—
100	69	36	69	40
150	65	53	80	44
200	78	47	50	20
250	67	55	10	11

influence exerted by the alkyl substituents in the hydrogenation of aromatics nucleus. The composition of the products from *o*-xylene and *p*-cymene are presented respectively in Tables 6 and 7.

TABLE 6—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE COMPOSITION OF PRODUCTS FROM *o*-XYLENE; CONTACT TIME 0.79 hr

Temp °C	Composition		
	<i>o</i> -Xylene unchanged	<i>trans</i> -Dimethyl-cyclohexane	<i>cis</i> -Dimethyl-cyclohexane
100	91	41	28
150	20	45	35
200	50	30	20
250	90	10	0.0

TABLE 7—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE COMPOSITION OF PRODUCTS FROM *p*-CYMENE; CONTACT TIME 0.79 hr

Temp °C	Composition (mole %)		
	<i>p</i> -Cymene unchanged	<i>trans</i> -Menthane	<i>cis</i> -Menthane
100	60	25	15
150	56	24	20
200	80	12	8.0
250	89	8.0	3.0

Among the compounds hydrogenated, benzene is found to be most active while *p*-cymene is least active as could be seen from the Table 5.

Introduction of alkyl groups into the benzene ring has been reported to slow down the rate of hydrogenation¹⁶. Accordingly, next to benzene, toluene is expected to undergo hydrogenation more rapidly than others. Contrary to the expectation it is *o*-xylene and not toluene underwent hydrogenation faster. Even though *o*-xylene seems to be

more reactive than toluene, its maximum activity remained only for a short temperature range followed by a sudden decrease while the other compounds maintained the maximum activity for longer temperature range, and then began to fall. In the case of toluene the amount hydrogenated keeps on steadily increasing. The reverse in the rate of hydrogenation of toluene and *o*-xylene is not clear. However the higher rate of conversion of *o*-xylene is believed to be due to the formation of *cis-trans*-isomers, the stable *trans*-isomer predominates over the *cis*-isomer which may be the real cause of the reverse order¹⁶.

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